

Identification And Quantification Of γ -Terpinene And Thymol From *Thymus Vulgaris* And *Thymus Serpyllum* And Their *In Vitro* Antiarthritic Activity

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ABSTRACT

The aim of present work *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* plants were collected, authenticated and their aerial parts were hydro-distilled to obtain extracts containing volatile oil. Initially preliminary phytochemical tests were performed for extracts, to confirm the presence of γ -terpinene and thymol. In order to quantify the γ -terpinene and thymol from the extracts of aerial parts of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* with help of standard markers γ -terpinene and thymol a GC-FID method was employed. The chromatographic conditions of the method employed an AB-Inowax capillary column (30m x 0.25mm x 0.25 μ m), using nitrogen as a carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.5ml/min. Injector and detector temperature was 250 and 300°C. The study was performed in split mode at a 1 μ l injection volume. The retention times of γ -terpinene and thymol were found to be 4.902 min and 12.045 min, respectively. Calibration curves were linear over the concentration range of (1-2.25 μ g/ml) for γ -terpinene and (2-4.5 μ g/ml) for thymol. Correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9944 for γ -terpinene and 0.9947 for thymol. This study aims to evaluate the antiarthritic activities which were determined by two different models, namely inhibition of protein denaturation and hyaluronidase inhibitory assay and showed antiarthritic activity at 12.5 μ g/ml-400 μ g/ml concentration. The percentage inhibition of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* were found to be 75.91 % and 70.92 %, respectively for inhibition of protein denaturation method and 80.42 % and 72.40 % for hyaluronidase inhibitory assay. The synergistic activity in the combined mixture of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* shows higher activity in both the model about 78.85 % and 82.88 %, respectively.

Keywords: *Thymus vulgaris*; *Thymus serpyllum*; Hydrodistillation; γ -terpinene; Thymol, Antiarthritic activity.

INTRODUCTION

Traditional systems of medicine have been steadily gaining importance and acceptance all over the world. Consequently, plant materials and herbal based drugs derived from them represent a substantial proportion of the current global drug market. In this scenario, there is a need to ensure that herbal drugs and preparations containing them possess optimum and consistent quality. Hence, there is a need to create and maintain a comprehensive quality assurance system. Quality control and standardization of herbal drugs are considered to be one of the major issues in herbal drug development¹.

A great number of herbs and spices can be found worldwide, with numerous originating from the Mediterranean area, either in the wild or cultivated, such as rosemary, oregano, sage, thymus, peppermint and garlic. Aromatic plants contain odorous, volatile, hydrophobic and highly concentrated compounds called essential oils (or volatile or ethereal oils). These are obtained from various parts of the plant such as flowers, buds, seeds, leaves, twigs, bark, wood, fruits and roots¹. *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* plants are contains rich in volatile oil. These two plants are belonging to the Lamiaceae family and

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native to Southern Europe. Both were located Western Ghats region also, particularly in Nilgiris Hills. The constituents of the ethereal oils are very much impact by intrinsic factors such as species, cultivar, clone and ecotype with ecological factors like geographical origin, climatic conditions, soil, biotic and technological factors. For these reasons, both plants are same family but dissimilar species, having different features and chemical compositions². *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* commonly known as Thyme and Wild Thyme. These two whole plants are traditionally important because it have many therapeutic values. Both are used as an antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, antiviral, antimicrobial agent and antibacterial in folk medicine since, the presence of thymol and γ - terpinene³⁻⁵. Rheumatoid arthritis, one of the common auto immune diseases, is a chronic, progressive and systemic inflammatory disorder affecting synovial joints producing symmetrical arthritis leading to joint degeneration⁸. Conventional herbal remedies are more sustainable in most of ethnic societies as compared to allopathic medicines because they are believed to be safest approach of treating diseases with least side effects on human health¹³⁻¹⁵.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals and reagents:

Biomarker of γ - terpinene (CAS.NO.99-85-4) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. It contains 97% purity and thymol was acquired from Loba Chemie Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. It contains 99-101 % purity. n-Hexane (GC grade solvent) was purchased from Nice Chemicals (P) Ltd., Kerala, India.

For *in-vitro* method, Bovine hyaluronidase was procured from Sigma-Aldrich, USA. Sodium hyaluronate was obtained from Zydus Research Centre, Ahmedabad, India. Bovine serum albumin was purchased from HI media, Maharashtra, India. Diclofenac sodium was purchased from Intas pharmaceuticals. Dimethyl sulfoxide, ammonium acetate, hydrochloric acid, p-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde, acetic acid, sodium hydroxide, sodium sulfate potassium borate, calcium chloride, ethanol, sodium chloride, potassium chloride, disodium hydrogen phosphate, potassium dihydrogen

phosphate and methanol were supplied by S.D. Fine Chemicals Ltd., and Merck Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai.

Distinguishing herbal drugs and extraction method:

The sample of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* were harvested in Western Ghats. The whole plants were collected from the Horticultural Research Station at Nilgiris Hills. The collected whole plants were identified and authenticated at Institute of Forest Genetics and Tree breeding, Indian Council of Forestry Research and Education, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu. The voucher specimen (Accession number 25239 and 25238) was deposited in Fischer Herbarium of the Institute of Forest Genetics and Tree Breeding, Coimbatore. The aerial parts of two plant materials were cleaned thoroughly, weighed 500g quantity and subjected to hydro distillation (3L of water) for 3-4 hours individually using Clevenger-type apparatus, the amount and percentage yields of extract were obtained 1.1 %w/v and 1 %w/v respectively. The Collected volatile oils were dehydrated by anhydrous sodium sulfate and stored in the tightly closed dark vial at 4°C separately until further analysis^{6,7}.

Essential oil chemical analysis:

Thymus vulgaris and *Thymus serpyllum* extracted oil were analyzed by make use of gas chromatography-flame ionization detector (GC-FID) technique¹².

Preparation of samples and standard solutions:

For *Thymus vulgaris* oil sample 20 mg/ml, for *Thymus serpyllum* oil sample 30 mg/ml were prepared in (GC grade solvent) n-hexane. For standards, a mixture of two standards (10 mg/ml of γ -terpinene and 20 mg/ml of thymol) was prepared in (GC grade solvent) n-hexane.

Chromatographic analysis (GC-FID):

The evaluation of the volatile oil were performed on a gas chromatography (GC) using a model 1100, (Mayura Analytical LLP, Bangalore), equipped with a flame ionization detector (FID). An AB- Inowax capillary polar column (polyethylene glycol: 30 m length; 0.25 mm i.d; 0.25 μ m film thickness) was used

and the flow rate of the carrier gas (N₂) was 1.5 ml/min. Analysis were performed using linear temperature program was employed to separate the different oil components. The oven temperature was kept at 50 °C for 1min, then raised to 230 °C at the rate of 10°C/min then was held constant 250 °C during 3min. Injector and detector temperatures were held at 250 °C and 300 °C correspondingly. Diluted samples of 1.0 µL were injected in the split mode (1:10 split). Quantification data were obtained electronically from FID without using any correction factors.

Antiarthritic studies of plant extracts:

It was carried out using two different *in-vitro* models namely inhibition of protein denaturation and hyaluronidase inhibitory activity by UV-VIS spectrophotometry method.

Inhibition of protein denaturation

Preparation of reagents:

Bovine serum albumin (BSA, 5 %) was prepared by dissolving 5 g of BSA in 100 ml of water. Phosphate buffer saline of pH 6.3 was prepared by dissolving 8 g of sodium chloride, 0.2 g of potassium chloride, 1.44 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate and 0.24 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 800 ml distilled water. The pH was adjusted to 6.3 using 1N HCl and the volume was made up to 1000 ml with distilled water.

Preparation of extracts:

Sufficient quantities of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* extract material were dissolved in n-hexane to get concentrations of 12.5, 25, 50, 100, 200 and 400 µg/ml respectively.

Procedure:

The reaction mixtures were prepared by adding bovine serum albumin (5 % v/v of aqueous solution) to 0.05 ml of extracts of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum*. And add standard diclofenac sodium individually in test tube. The total volume of each reaction mixture was fixed as 0.5 ml and pH was adjusted to 6.3 make use of 1N HCl. The samples

were incubated at 37 °C for 20 min and then heated at 57 °C for 3 min. After cooling the samples, 2.5 ml phosphate buffer saline (pH 6.3) was added to each tube. Absorbance was determined by spectrophotometrically at 296 nm. A control test was performed treating 0.05 ml distilled water in place of extracts while product control tests without bovine serum albumin. The rate of inhibition of protein denaturation was calculated as follows:

Percentage Inhibition (%) = $100 \times \frac{\text{absorbance of control} - (\text{absorbance of test} - \text{absorbance of product control})}{\text{absorbance of control}}$

The control represents 100% protein denaturation. The results of the extract were compared with the results of diclofenac treated samples. The inhibition of protein denaturation was expressed as percentage of inhibition and the IC₅₀ values determined by linear regression plots with varying concentration of plants extracts against percentage inhibition. Study of biological activity of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* by *in-vitro* methods were carried out and reported.

Hyaluronidase inhibitory assay

Preparation of reagents:

A 5 % DMSO was prepared by mixing 5ml of the DMSO solution in 100 ml of water. About 0.1M ammonium acetate buffer of pH 3.5 was prepared by dissolving 2.5 g of ammonium acetate in 2.5 ml of water, 3.8 ml of 7M HCl was added, the pH was adjusted to 3.5 with 2M HCl and finally the volume was made upto 1000 ml with water. 4 g of p-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde was dissolved in 350 ml of 100% acetic acid and 50 ml of 10N hydrochloric acid was added.

Procedure:

Hydrodistillation extracts were prepared from *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum*, which were examined for their inhibitory effects on the enzyme hyaluronidase. About 50 µl of Bovine hyaluronidase (7900 units/ml) was dissolved in 0.1M acetate buffer (pH 3.5) and mixed with 100 µl of a designated concentration of sample (extracts of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum*) dissolved 5 %v/v of dimethyl

sulfoxide. Then the mixture was incubated in a water bath at 37 °C for 20 minutes. The control group was treated similarly with 100 µl of 5 % v/v of DMSO instead of the sample. About 100 µl of 12.5mM CaCl₂ solution was added to the reaction mixture and then the mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 20 minutes. The Ca²⁺ activated hyaluronidase was treated with 250 µl of sodium hyaluronate (1.2 mg/ml) dissolved in 0.1M acetate buffer (pH 3.5) and then incubated in a water bath at 37 °C for 40 minutes. About 100 µl of 0.4N NaOH and 100 µl of 0.4N K₃BO₃ were treated to the reaction mixture and then incubated in a boiling water bath for 3 minutes. After cooling to room temperature, 3 ml of p-dimethyl amino benzaldehyde solution was add on to the reaction mixture which was then incubated in a water bath at 37 °C for 20 minutes. Absorbance was read at 440 nm for the reaction mixture, by utilizing a spectrophotometer. The percentage inhibition was calculated as:

$$\text{Percentage inhibition (\%)} = \frac{(\text{absorbance of control} - \text{absorbance of sample})}{\text{absorbance of control}} \times 100.$$

The hyaluronidase inhibition activity was expressed as percentage of inhibition and the IC₅₀ values determined by linear regression plots with varying concentration of plants extract against percentage inhibition. Study of biological activity of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* by *invitro* methods were carried out and reported^{9,10}.

Statistical analysis:

All the experiments were conducted in three replicates and the data were presented as mean ± standard deviation of triplicate determinations. The IC₅₀ values were calculated from the linear regression analysis. The comparison between concentration of oil extract against the percentage inhibition was assessed applying one-way ANOVA test. The findings were observed statistically significant if (P< 0.05)¹⁶.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The determination of γ -terpinene and thymol content in two plant extracts. A steady baseline was recorded with the fixed chromatographic conditions. The extracts were injected, individual constituents separated and recorded the chromatograms. γ -terpinene and thymol were confirmed by standard chromatogram using retention time (Figure 1 to 3).

From *Thymus vulgaris* oil was obtained totally 14 compounds, in that 5th and 13th compounds were identified γ -terpinene (4.980) and thymol (12.073), Peak area of both the standards were exhibited 924491, 2537504 respectively. From *Thymus serpyllum* oil was obtained totally 8 compounds, in that 2nd and 7th compounds were identified γ -terpinene (4.958) and thymol (12.096), Peak area of both the standards were exhibited 735374, 2735219 respectively.

Calibration curves were linear over the concentration range of (1-2.25 µg/ml) for γ- terpinene and (2-4.5 µg/ml) for thymol. Correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9944 for γ- terpinene and 0.9947 for thymol (Figure 4).

Figure 1. Standard mixture of γ-terpinene (1mg/ml) and thymol (2mg/ml)

Figure 2. GC chromatogram of *Thymus vulgaris* extract (20mg/ml)

Figure 3. GC chromatogram of *Thymus serpyllum* extract (30mg/ml)

Figure 4. Calibration graph of γ -terpinene and thymol

Study of biological activity of plant extracts:

Evaluation of various combinations of the plant extracts were undertaken to assess their antiarthritic potentials. It was found that combination of a *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* extracts exhibited

good activity. The absorbance of the mixture was measured at 296 nm for assessing the inhibition of protein denaturation activity and absorbance at 440 nm for evaluation of hyaluronidase inhibitory activity. The percentage inhibitions are presented in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Model 1 – Inhibition of protein denaturation activity

Combination	12.5 μ g/ml	25 μ g/ml	50 μ g/ml	100 μ g/ml	200 μ g/ml	400 μ g/ml	IC ₅₀ μ g/ml
Mixture	34.67 \pm 0.01	40.65 \pm 0.02	52.10 \pm 0.10	59.27 \pm 0.11	67.13 \pm 0.08	78.85 \pm 0.12	48.57 \pm 0.02
Diclofenac	44.09 \pm 0.09	63.42 \pm 0.1	71.70 \pm 0.4	87.60 \pm 0.3	90.07 \pm 0.17	92.58 \pm 0.11	17.5 \pm 0.03

Table 1: Model 2 – Hyaluronidase inhibitory assay

Combination	12.5 μ g/ml	25 μ g/ml	50 μ g/ml	100 μ g/ml	200 μ g/ml	400 μ g/ml	IC ₅₀ μ g/ml
Mixture	45.75 \pm 0.31	52.71 \pm 0.41	65.54 \pm 0.30	68.91 \pm 0.20	72.96 \pm 0.22	82.88 \pm 0.32	22 \pm 0.41

The extracts showed promising inhibition of protein denaturation and hyaluronidase, indicating potential antiarthritic effects.

*Average of three determinations

Figure 5. Percentage inhibition of combined plant extracts of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* in protein denaturation

*Average of three determinations

Figure 6. Percentage inhibition of combined plant extracts of *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* in Hyaluronidase inhibitory assay

CONCLUSION

The biological activity of the medicinal plants was investigated by carrying out the antiarthritic activity on individual extracts. The antiarthritic activity was carried out based on the principle of denaturation of protein and hyaluronidase enzyme by applying individual procedure. Denaturation of protein study

shows that the *Thymus vulgaris* has high inhibition of 75.91 % at 400 µg/ml concentration, and hyaluronidase inhibition study also reported the same. *Thymus vulgaris* has high inhibition of 80.42 % at 400 µg/ml concentration. So, *Thymus vulgaris* was found to show better activity than other extract. The plant extracts were combined to exhibit their synergistic activities on antiarthritic properties. Based on the

activity of individual extracts, combine mixture were prepared that *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum* to apply the hyaluronidase inhibition procedure have high inhibition of 82.88 % at concentration 400 µg/ml. The result outcome of this research paper would support herbal industries and phytochemical researches to use this as foremost authority documents. Since, to the best of our knowledge, no such studies have investigated in the literature for the two plants viz., *Thymus vulgaris* and *Thymus serpyllum*. "The *invitro* assays suggest that these compounds may contribute to antiarthritic effects, which opens possibilities for further pharmacological studies. Further *invivo* studies and clinical trials are recommended to explore the full therapeutic potential of these phytochemicals."

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REFERENCES

1. Chaudhury RR. Herbal medicine for human health. World Health Organization Geneva. CBS publishers and distributors LTD, New Delhi, 1999
2. Christaki, E., Bonos, E., Giannenas, I. and Florou-Paneri, P. (2012). A review on an Aromatic Plants as a Source of Bioactive Compounds. Agriculture, 2: 228-243
3. Li, X., He, T., Wang, X., Shen, M., Yan, X., Fan, S., Wang, L., Wang, X., Xu, X., Sui, H. and She, G. (2019). A review on Traditional Uses, Chemical Constituents and Biological Activities of Plants from the Genus *Thymus*, Chem. Biodiverse 16(9):e1900254
4. Miura, K. and Nakatani, N., (1989). Antioxidant activity of flavonoids from thyme (*Thymus vulgaris* L). Agri Biol Chem. 53 (11):3043-3045
5. Kar A. Pharmacognosy and Pharmacobiotechnology. (2007). 2nd ed. New Delhi: New Age International Pvt. Ltd; 215-328.
6. Tambare, P., Tamboli, FA. and More, HN. (2021). An overview of the standardization of herbal drugs. J Pharm Educ Res. 3(1): 09-12
7. Charles, DJ. and Simon, JE. (1990). Comparison of Extraction Methods for the Rapid Determination of Essential Oil Content and Composition of Basil. J Amer Soc Hort Sci. 115(3):458-62.
8. Jayaprakasam, R., Philip, N., Vinod, S., Jacob, L. and Ravi, TK. (2015). HPTLC method for the simultaneous estimation of stigmasterol and β -sitosterol in *Abroma Augusta*. Roots and its *in vitro* biological activity screening. Indian Drug Manuf Assoc. 52 (2):12-19.
9. Salaria, D., Rolta, R., Prakash, A., Fadare, OA., Jachak, S. and Medhi, B. (2021). *In vitro* and *in silico* analysis of *Thymus serpyllum* essential oil as bioactivity enhancer of antibacterial and antifungal agents. Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics. 1-20.
10. Ratnasooriya, WD., Abeysekera, WPKM. and Ratnasooriya, CTD. (2014). *In vitro* antihyaluronidase activity of Sri lankan low grown orthodox orange pekoe grade black tea (*Camellia sinensis*). Asian Pac Trop Biomed. 4(2):959-63.
11. Haloci, E., Toska, V., Vertuani, S. and Meto, (2014). Development and validation of a GC-FID method for identification and quantification of main components of *Satureja montana* essential oil. Int J Pharm Pharm Sci. 6(2):302-06.
12. Seema, CC. and Meena, V. (2011). Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-arthritis activity of *Centella asiatica*. J Chem Biol Phys Sci. 1(2):260-69.
13. Baj, T. (2020). Chemical composition and *invitro* activity of *Origanum vulgare*, *Satureja hortensis*, *Thymus serpyllum* and *Thymus vulgaris* essential oils towards oral isolates of *Candida albicans* and *Candida glabrata*. Open Chem. 18: 08-11.
14. Navuluri, S., Elumalai, A., Chinna, EM. And Naresh, V. (2012). An updated review on anti-arthritis medicinal plants. Int J Pharm Rev Res. 2(1):11-15.
15. Althaher, A. R., Oran, S. A., and Bustanji, Y. K. (2020). Phytochemical Analysis, *In vitro* Assessment of Antioxidant Properties and Cytotoxic Potential of *Ruta chalepensis* L. Essential Oil. Journal of Essential Oil Bearing Plants, 23(6):1409-1421..

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